

EMERGING ISSUES AND CHALLENGES IN DIGITALIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION –VIKASITH BHARATH

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Abstract

India holds the second position in the world of having highest population. Indian women generally faced all types of barriers to success like illiteracy, domestic violence, lack of motivation and support and many more. India is country where man dominance in the society Prevails. It is very essential for the harmonious development of the country that women should go hand by hand and shoulder to shoulder with men. And for empowering the women, higher education will play a vital role.

Higher Education is one of the most important means of empowering women with the knowledge, skills and self-confidence necessary to participate fully in the development process. Higher educational provide opportunities to women to fulfill their Needs. These needs comprise both essential learning tools (such as literacy, oral expression, numeracy and problem solving) and the basic learning content such as knowledge, skills, values and attitudes required by human beings to be able to survive, to develop their full capacities, to live and work in dignity, to participate fully in development, to improve the quality of their lives, to make informed decision making and to continue learning.

Introduction:

"To educate your women first and leave them to themselves, They will tell you what reforms are necessary." ---- Swami Vivekananda.

Education of women in India has been a major issue for both the government and civil society, as the educated women play a very important role in the development of the country. India, at present has largest number of illiterates in the world.

A higher women literacy rate improves the quality of life both at home and outside home, by encouraging and promoting education of children, especially female children, and

helps in reducing the infant mortality rate. It is true that empowerment can be gained with the help of education because it gives the knowledge of right and wrong, truth and lie.

Women constitute almost half the human race. Education has been recognized as an essential agent of social change and development in any society of any country. Education is considered as a potential instrument through which processes of modernization and social change come to existence. Education exposes people to new thoughts and ideas which provides necessary skills.

According to the Government of India, "Empowerment means moving from a weak position to execute a power." It is the ability to direct and control one's life. It is a process in which women gain control over their own lives of knowing and claiming their right at all levels of society at the international, local and household levels. Women also bear almost all responsibility for meeting basic needs of the family

Meaning of Women Empowerment:

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The absence of a democratic context has contributed to slow progress in empowering women, particularly in South Asia. Women's empowerment movements have not survived in authoritarian regimes based on gender subordination and ideologies of male dominance. Approaches in South Asia have necessarily focused on opportunities and services rather than on political power. Conceptualizations of gender discrimination and male domination have been oversimplified and focused on elimination of obvious oppressive practices such as wife beating or dowry demands. Empowerment of women that will have lasting impacts must involve consciousness raising before the social construction of gender, which subordinates women in the family, class, caste, religion, or society, can be changed. Three experimental approaches to empowerment in South Asia have been tried: integrated development, economic empowerment, and consciousness raising. Consciousness raising has been implemented in awareness groups and education that have led to a new consciousness, self worth, societal and gender analysis, and access to skills and information. The economic empowerment approach has relied on improving women's control over economic resources and strengthening women's economic security. Women were encouraged to find a separate time and space for themselves. The three aforementioned approaches have different assumptions about the reason for women's powerlessness: greater poverty and lower access to

resources, economic vulnerability, and subordination within patriarchal societies and socioeconomic inequalities.

Meaning of Higher Education:

Higher Education is the aggregate of systematized knowledge and practical skills that allow theoretical and practical problems to be solved by a given type of training, utilizing and creatively developing the modern achievements of science, technology, and culture. The term “higher education” is also applied to the training of highly skilled specialists in the fields of economics, science, technology, and culture at various types of higher schools, which accept persons who have successfully completed secondary general-education schools or secondary specialized-education institutions.

Objectives of the Study:

To study the economic benefit of women empowerment through Education. To study the role of higher education in the empowerment of women

Women education:

“If you educate a man you educate an individual, however, if you educate a woman you educate a whole family. Women empowered means mother India empowered”.

JAWAHARLAL NEHRU

India is poised to emerge as one of the most developed nations by 2020, more literate, knowledgeable and economically at the forefront. No doubt, women will play a vital role in contributing to the country's development. Women power is crucial to the economic growth of any country. In India this is yet to meet the requirements despite reforms. Little has been achieved in the area of women empowerment, but for this to happen, this sector must experience a chain of reforms. Though India could well become one of the largest economies in the world, it is being hindered due to a lack of women's participation.

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The Role of Higher Education in the Empowerment of Women:

To be involved in the dialogue about education systems around the world today is to understand and articulate the key role played by higher education. Through higher education flow of the ideology, values, and culture of a nation, state, and its people. Misinformation and constricted learning behaviors that women internalize can also be filtered through higher education.

Women education in India plays a very important role in the overall development of the country. It not only helps in the development of half of the human resources, but in improving the quality of life at home and outside. Educated women not only tend to promote education of their girl children, but also can provide better guidance to all their children. Moreover educated women can also help in the reduction of infant mortality rate and growth of the population.

Importance of women higher education in India:

"Higher Education is one of the most important means of empowering women with the knowledge, skills and self-confidence necessary to participate fully in the development process."

Higher Education is important for everyone, but it is especially significant for girls and women. This is true not only because Higher education is an entry point to other opportunities, but also because the Higher educational achievements of women can have ripple effects within the family and across generations. Investing in girls' education is one of the most effective ways to reduce poverty.

Girls who have been Higher education are likely to marry later and to have smaller and healthier families. Educated women can recognize the importance of health care and know how to seek it for themselves and their children.

Women's literacy rates are significantly lower than men's in most developing countries. Higher Education helps girls and women to know their rights and to gain confidence to claim them and achieve better position in the society.

The Higher education of parents is linked to their children's educational attainment, and the mother's education is usually more influential than the father's. An educated mother's greater influence in household negotiations may allow her to secure more resources for her children.

India is a developing country and facing a problem of high population, family planning is very important concept, educated mothers, averaging fewer children, can concentrate more attention on each child.

Conclusion:

Higher Education is one of the most important means of empowering women with the knowledge, skills and self-confidence necessary to participate fully in the development process.

Higher Education also brings a reduction in inequalities and functions as a means of improving their status within the family. For reducing gender biasness, encouraging women to make good society and to become the strongest part of the economy.

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